

BLENDID LEARNING METHOD AS A TREND IN MODERN EDUCATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14209216>

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ABSTRACT

An educational strategy known as blended learning blends information and traditional learning technology. This teaching approach is thoroughly examined in the article, along with its primary techniques, benefits, and issues related to its current use in educational institutions. In our nation, blended learning is still in its early stages of development. Every model of this instruction entails a substantial modification of the teaching methodology. If the majority of the time in the traditional classroom lesson system is dedicated to upholding discipline and developing educational skills and abilities, then in mixed learning, the focus is primarily on the development of individual and group work skills as well as the building of communicative competences.

Key words: *feasible, provide, assistance, flipped, systematic, utilize, schedule, autonomously, reallocate, digital resources*

The dominance of information and communication technologies in the educational process characterizes its current stage of growth, which intensifies the use of conventional forms and techniques of instruction. Many educators believe that blended learning—also known as hybrid or integrated learning—is a wonderful innovation of the twenty-first century for the educational system. It is the case and, based on projections, it will stay that way for the next ten years or more.

Regarding the notion of blended learning, this is a direct translation of the terms "blended learning" from English into Russian. Since 2006, this kind of training has been developed most aggressively in the United States, where it is also most frequently used.

The following statistics attest to this: if just 40,000 students in the US used blended learning in 2000, by 2009 there were already 3 million, and by 2019, it is anticipated that 50% of all classrooms would use this technology. These days, Europe and Southeast Asia are also big users of blended learning technologies. The concept of blended learning is still in its infancy in Russia and our own nation.

"Blended learning is an instructional strategy that combines traditional teaching technologies (online learning and instructor-led instruction) with information; more specifically, these technologies appear to enhance one another. This method works under the assumption that students independently choose the direction, location, schedule, and speed of their education. Online learning and supervised learning experiences are also combined in this course. In Russia, N., V. Andreeva, L., V. Rozhdestvenskaya, and B. Yarmakhov are experts in blended learning. The 2016 book "The School Step into Blended Learning," written by them, was released. These individuals are experts that have extensive experience in blended learning.[Andreeva,2016]

Blended learning doesn't need any models at the beginning. The instructor employs computer technology and information at his own discretion to address specific issues. The educational process often doesn't change all that much at the beginning. Certain models are already beginning to form as a result of more systematic application. More than 40 blended learning approaches are listed by the innovation-driven research and development organization, Clayton Christensen Institute. Naturally, not all of them have the same level of popularity or efficacy. The four blended learning models that instructors utilize the most frequently nowadays are as follows.

Flipped classrooms are the first model. This model is described as a two-part educational process. Two forms of learning are interactive group learning that takes place in a classroom or auditorium with the assistance of a teacher or instructor, and independent learning that takes place outside of the classroom with computer technology (e.g., self-studying an online course at home). The implementation of this concept appears to be an inversion of the educational process, as fresh content is studied freely at home via online courses. Specific challenging times are thoroughly explored in class. The following illustrates this model's benefits:

First, the student has unrestricted access to difficult course content; second, learning happens at their own speed. If a student encounters any difficulties while studying the material on their own at home, they bring their specific questions and issues to class or the auditorium. Students can then autonomously reallocate their time to the areas that they still struggle with and do not fully comprehend. With the help of this paradigm, you can transition from frontal learning—which takes place in a classroom or a university auditorium—to individual learning. This is made feasible by the teacher's ability to swiftly modify the lesson plan based on data regarding the effectiveness of learning new material at home. For instance, a teacher can work with pupils who have absorbed the course material poorly or have not fully, and prepare a role-play for those who have mastered it. The teacher has access to information about

success or failure that is stored on the remote learning platform (Moodle, Classroom). The station rotation model, which rotates work areas, is the next model. Its fundamental idea is that a classroom or classrooms be set up with at least three stations set up at the same time. Every group is given a "route sheet," which includes a specific assignment and the final objective of working at the station. Only three to four persons in a group are thought to be the most productive.

At the first station, the instructor works one-on-one with the class (frontal work). This gives him the chance to identify any students who may be lacking in knowledge and, if feasible, provide assistance. Students work independently on a mini-project (group projects) at the second station. Simultaneously, an online component that happens at the third station must be completed. Every station may operate for ten to fifteen minutes. There are planned transitions between every station. Representatives from each group visit each station after work to present their projects. Work with a teacher or teachers and an online course could be the two stations. In this instance, project work is completed within the third or fourth lesson at the latest. [Brew, 2008]

There are also options with four stations. Individual, independent effort is added in this instance. The laboratory rotation model is the third model. Because this concept involves an online course, it is comparable to a flipped classroom. There are parallels between this model and the "station rotation" paradigm as well. In this instance, only stations develop into full laboratories. Simultaneously, multiple educators concur on the establishment of these identical laboratories. Additionally, they are creating a new online course that students can take at their own pace. In addition to forming a single classroom under this approach, instructors also concur with the school administration that a third or fourth lesson will be dedicated to project activities.

The fourth model, which goes by the names "Personal choice," "New profile," and "Individual curriculum," is a flexible paradigm. This is the most promising paradigm, but it is also the most challenging to implement. The challenge is that kids need to possess strong self-organization abilities. The actual organization of the learning environment may also present challenges. Typically, this resembles a central classroom (a setting or location for virtual education and group projects). Students also have their own private mini-offices, training labs, project rooms, and facilities for socializing and communication (laboratories and group work offices). [Kingma, 2006]

This model's basic tenet is that students can engage in any kind of activity for as long as they choose. Instead, each person has a flexible work schedule that they can alter whenever they see fit. There aren't many limitations in the flexible model that are present in the educational process. There isn't really a lesson, nor are there any

room limits or other limitations. The ability for each student to learn at his own pace is the most crucial aspect of education. This model's basic tenet is that students can engage in any kind of activity for as long as they choose. Instead, each person has a flexible work schedule that they can alter whenever they see fit. There aren't many limitations in the flexible model that are present in the educational process. There isn't really a lesson, nor are there any room limits or other limitations. The ability for each student to learn at his own pace is the most crucial aspect of education. Thus, you may think of the blended learning approach as a tool that helps you make better use of the benefits of both in-person and online learning, or that balances out the drawbacks of both. Teachers and educators employ a variety of digital educational tools and internet services while implementing blended learning methods. Teachers' own materials as well as pre-made digital resources are used. Simultaneously, methodologists recommend that complete electronic resources be prioritized since they offer tools for structuring the educational process as well as educational content that satisfies all requirements.

Blended learning is without a doubt a very powerful educational tool with a plethora of applications both in the present and the future. This is because, with appropriate and effective use of this technology, such training will help pupils develop highly crucial and desirable personality traits. These competencies mostly consist of:

- the capacity to think critically;
- the ability to handle complicated problems;
- the capacity to locate the data required to address a particular issue;
- the capacity for creative thought;
- the capacity for teamwork, or the ability to interact with others to discover solutions to problems;
- the drive to learn new things throughout life;
- the capacity for making wise decisions and accepting accountability for them.

Many refer to all of these abilities and characteristics as 21st-century personality traits. As you can see, the application of this training in the educational process is crucial. Nevertheless, a lot of teachers aren't prepared for it as, similar to other cutting-edge technologies, blended learning takes time to adopt and involves a lot of extra work from the teacher to establish the group's or class's learning culture.

If the majority of the time in a traditional classroom lesson plan is devoted to fostering academic skills and abilities as well as upholding discipline, then in a mixed learning environment, the focus is primarily on the development of students' abilities to work independently and in groups as well as the formation of their communicative competencies. Since using computers is a requirement for implementing blended

learning, dependence on technology is undoubtedly another significant issue with not utilizing this technology. These could be fully functional computer rooms (auditoria) with continuous Internet access (broadband Internet and a reliable online mode are necessary) or student-owned mobile devices with limitless data. Due to the unavailability of these gadgets, teachers frequently have to organize their own online instruction at home. Some educators clarify that the rigorous integration of training sessions into the curriculum makes it impossible to use this technology. The low degree of IT proficiency is another barrier to this technology's adoption. The LMS platform (learning management system, which is utilized as an IT platform / software application with a variety of features in online learning or e-education) must be learned to use by both teachers and students.

Naturally, implementing blended learning means that the legal framework will need to be changed, technological support will be needed, and there will be time and money expenditures involved in creating video materials, training curricula, testing modules, and staff retraining.

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